

were transplanted in pots for disease development. Successive inoculation and access feeding on treated plants continued until the death of all the viruliferous insects. Symptoms in inoculated seedlings were observed on day 12.

The randomized complete-block design experiment was replicated 5 times using 440 viruliferous insects and 440 treated seedlings for 11 treatments. A total of 2,200 viruliferous insects and 4,667 treated seedlings were used.

Both oils reduced insect survival and RTV transmission. One day after feeding, 95.5% of the insects survived in the control. Survival was significantly less on all oil-sprayed plants — the higher the oil concentration, the lower the insect survival (Table 1) — but differences in insect survival at different oil concentrations were not significant.

Two days after feeding, insect survival on the control averaged 86.5%. In the custard-apple oil treatment at 30% concentration, only 1.5% of the insects survived; at 50% concentration, none survived. In neem oil treatments, 2.5% of the insects survived at both concentrations. Three days after feeding, insect survival was near zero in most treatments.

Transmission of RTV by the viruliferous insect to oil-sprayed TN1 rice seedlings was represented by the number of infected seedlings. One-day inoculation feeding infected 60.4% of the control seedlings. Infection of oil-sprayed

Table 1. Survival of *Nephotettix virescens* after 1, 2, and 3 days exposure to TN1 rice seedlings sprayed with oils^a at IIRRI.

Oil concentration (%)	Survival (%) of <i>N. virescens</i> ^b					
	1 d		2 d		3 d	
	C-ao	No	C-ao	No	C-ao	No
5	25.0 b	57.5 b	5.0 b	23.5 b	0	7.0 b
10	27.5 b	36.5 cd	5.5 bc	16.5 bc	0.5 b	5.5 b
20	22.5 bc	42.0 c	6.0 b	8.0 bc	1.0 b	0 b
30	16.5 bc	34.0 cd	1.5 b	2.5 c	0 b	0 b
50	1.5 c	26.6 d	0 b	2.5 c	0 b	0 b
0 (control: water + 0.1% liquid detergent)	95.5 a	95.5 a	86.5 a	86.5 a	80.0 a	80.0 a

^aC-ao = custard-apple oil, No = neem oil. ^bIn a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Table 2. Rice tungro virus (RTV) infection on TN1 rice seedlings sprayed with oils^a after 1 and 2 days exposure to viruliferous insects at IIRRI.

Oil concentration (%)	RTV infection (%) of TN1 seedlings ^b			
	1 d		2 d	
	C-ao	No	C-ao	No
5	25.0 b	27.0 b	6.9 b	13.6 b
10	19.0 bc	16.4 bc	4.2 b	11.2 b
20	19.0 bc	20.9 bc	2.4 b	10.2 b
30	20.4 bc	13.6 c	11.0 b	4.5 b
50	10.5 c	11.8 c	0.2 b	10.3 b
0 (control: water + 0.1% liquid detergent)	60.4 a	60.4 a	35.5 a	35.5 a

^aC-ao = custard-apple oil, No = neem oil. ^bIn a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

seedlings was significantly less at all concentrations of both oils (Table 2).

After 2 days of inoculation feeding, 35.5% of the control seedlings were infected; significantly less infection occurred in all oil treatments. Both oils at 5% concentration significantly

reduced RTV infection of TN1 seedlings, on par with infection levels at higher concentrations. After 3 days of feeding, only a few plants were infected. After 4 days of feeding, no seedlings were infected because no insects survived on oil-sprayed plants. ■

Effect of foliar insecticides on stem borers and leaffolders

R. Saroja and N. Raju, Paddy Experiment Station, Tirur 602025, Tamil Nadu, India

The effect of six foliar insecticides on rice stem borers and leaffolders was studied at Tirur during the 1980-81 samba season. The field trial was laid out in a simple randomized block design with three replications. IR8 seedlings 35 days old were planted in 12-m² plots at 20 × 10-cm spacing. Insecticides were sprayed at 45 and 60 days after transplanting (DT).

Deadhearts (stem borer damage) in

Effect of new foliar insecticides on rice stem borers and leaffolders. Tirur, India. 1980-81 samba.

Treatment	Formulation	Quantity applied (kg a.i./ha)	Stem borer deadhearts 75 DT		Leaffolder damage 15 DT		Grain yield (t/ha)
			No.	Square root	%	Angles	
			Carbosulfan	24 EC	0.4	18.8	
Bendiocarb	80 WP	0.5	12.0	3.47	2.5	9.03	6.1
BPMC	20 EC	0.5	26.9	5.19	23.9	29.29	5.1
Acephate	75 SP	0.5	6.8	2.61	4.2	11.76	6.1
Vamidothion	30 EC	0.5	37.6	6.13	35.8	36.79	3.9
Ethion	50 EC	0.5	29.8	5.46	48.2	43.95	3.1
Control	—	—	35.5	5.96	68.9	56.11	1.8
CD	—	—	—	1.32	—	9.52	1.5

each plot and leaf damage (leaffolders) on 50 hills/plot were assessed at 75 DT (see table). Bendiocarb, acephate, and carbosulfan were more effective in

checking both stem borer and leaffolder. Their use gave higher yields than did three other chemicals and no treatment. ■